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FORMULATION OF A SNAIL-PROTEIN RICH MAIZE BASE WEANING FOOD (NutriPACK)

By

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this Project was to formulate an enriched snail-protein rich maize based food from locally and readily available raw materials. Through an experimental design, dried snails, maize, soy beans and crayfish were transformed by grinding into flour and content mixed to homogeneity following proportions of (%w/w) 40:30:25:5, 43:33:20:4 and 20:55:20:5 of carbohydrate, protein soybeans, snails and crayfish respective, considering FAO/WHO standards for infant food formulations. Evaluation of the sensory properties by a trained sensory analysis panel was carried out on the final product. Proximate analysis on the nutrient properties of the product was studied and quantified as described in ANFOR 1981 and 1984 with protein assayed following colorimetric techniques. Determination of shelf life of the product was done by assessment of the microbial load over time using several dilutions of samples as described by APHA. Coliform counts determined with violet red bile (VRB), Total Bacterial load with Nutrient Agar (Sigma - Aldrich) and Total Fungal load by ISO horizontal methods as described by ISO 8786.1 USING Sabouraud Dextrose agar. Appropriate packaging was realized as per ISO standards of 9001. 2005 to ensure quality, safety and efficiency of the product. Results show that the carbohydrate content of the best sample following sensory analysis (Sample 1) was 48.26g/100g Pdt, the protein content, 21.97g/100g Pdt, the fat content, 10.93g/100g Pdt, the Ash (mineral) content, 2.97mg/100g Pdt, the Energy content 15.4Kcal and the Dry matter, 86.60mg/100g Pdt. The most abundant mineral was calcium 87.03mg/100g Pdt, followed by Magnesium, 16.00mg/100g Pdt, Iron, 3.20mg/100gPdt. Sample one which was the best sample was assessed for its microbial and shelf-life quality. The weaning food had no microbe at week zero. After six weeks, the bacterial load ranged from 7.7 to 227.2 × 10⁻⁵ Cfug, coliform load from 2.2 to 70.4 × 10⁻⁵ Cfug and fungal load from 1 to 6 × 10⁻⁶ Cfug. and continued progressively to Lethal point. The product is packaged following the Codex Standards to preserve the hygienic and other qualities of the food.

Keywords: Weaning food, Proximal composition, Minerals, Microbiological load, Packaging

1 Introduction

Weaning foods have been inadequately introduced especially in the rural areas. Most nursing mothers are known for the introduction of bulk foods as weaning foods and, are not taking into consideration their nutritional value based on children's nutritional needs. The inappropriate introduction of weaning foods in most areas is sometimes due to the high costs prices levied on fortified weaning foods like cerelac, phosphatine, etc.

The introduction of appropriate weaning foods that provide sufficient energy and micronutrients to promote optimal growth and development, should be affordable and sustainable, weaning foods for infants are very much needed for growth and maintenance.

Locally available food crops can be used to formulate nutritious weaning foods that can contribute towards alleviating under nutrition and improve children's development (Mitra, 2012). Weaning foods should meet the nutrient requirement of rapidly growing children and the food should be diverse with appropriate texture and given in sufficient quantity.

Formulating and development of nutritious weaning foods from locally and readily available raw materials have received a lot of attention in many developing countries. Apart from protein and energy, infants diet need calcium, iron and trace elements which can be obtained by combining local staples presently available in the country. Soybeans is rich in protein (40%) and fats (20%) (Bender and Bender, 1999). Raw materials of most commercial weaning foods are not locally available. since most commercially available weaning foods are expensive so not affordable by low income mothers, the problem of malnutrition in infants can be solved by introduction of nutritious quality weaning foods, crayfish, maize, snails, soybeans and table sugar used for diet formulation in this study, are locally produced in large quantities in Cameroon yet children still die of hunger.

The aim of this study was to assess the proximal and microbial quality of locally formulated Snail - Protein maize based weaning food, as well as design a package for its possible commercialization.

2 Material and Method

2.1 Material

The materials used are Maize, Soybeans, Crayfish, and Snails was purchased in the local market in Kumba.

2.2 Method

This project used an experimental research design to investigate the proximal and microbial qualities for shelf-life determination of a locally formulated protein rich maize based weaning food. It also sought to design a food package for the commercialization of the weaning food. The data

was analysed using descriptive statistics (that is tabulation and percentages). All determinations were carried out in triplicate and data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA). Statistical analysis was performed using SigmaStat version 3.5 (Point Richmond, CA, USA). Multiple comparison within variables was performed using the Turkey test post hoc. Statistical significance between parameters was set at probability (p) value < 0.05. The above materials were prepared as follows:

2.2.1 Preparation of Soybeans Flour

Source: Field work, 2023

Figure 1: Flow Diagram for Processing Soybean Flour

2.2.2 Preparation of Crayfish Flour

Crayfish was bought from the market. It was sorted to remove stones, dry leaves, sticks and other unwanted materials. It was then sun dried. Crayfish was grinded using normal hand grinding machine. After grinding it was sieved to obtain the crayfish fine flour then packaged and stored.

2.2.3 Preparation of Maize Flour

Maize was bought, sorted and soaked in water. It was then sundried, fried and ground using a grinding mill. Finally, it was sieved to obtain fine maize flour which was then packaged and stored.

2.2.4 Preparation of Snails Flour

Snails were bought, removed from shell and broken to remove the other parts like eyes and ears, washed thoroughly to remove all the sticky slimy fluid coming from the snails and parboiled, dried under the sun for about a week until it becomes crispy to ease grinding. They were further grinded using a grinding mill and sieved to obtain the snail fine flour.

2.2.5 Total Ash Content (Total Minerals)

The total ash was quantified by the method described in AFNOR, 1981. The ash content per 100g of DM was calculated using the formula: Total ash (%) = $\frac{m_3 - m_0}{m_2 - m_0} \times 100$

2.2.6 Determination of total sugar content

The determination of the total extracted sugars was measured according to the (DNS) method described by Fischer and Stein (1961). In an alkaline and hot medium, DNS reacts with the extracted sugars and changes from its yellow oxidized form to its orange reduced form with maximum absorption at 530nm. The optical density of the solution was read at 540nm using a spectrophotometer and recorded.

2.2.7 Protein content

The total nitrogen is determined after mineralization of the samples according to the Kjeldahl method (AFNOR, 1984) and assayed using a calorimetric technique (Devani *et al.*, 1989).

2.2.8 Lipid content

The total lipids in the corn samples were extracted with a Soxhlet according to the Russian method described by Bourely, (1982). The oil content (Ph) per 100g of sample, expressed at 0% moisture was calculated using the formula:

$$\%Ph = [(P - P2) / (P1 - P2)] \times 100$$

2.2.9 Determination of Iron Content

The iron is assayed with orthophenanthroline by colorimetry according to the method of Rodier, (1978).

2.2.10 Determination of calcium and magnesium contents of the weaning food

The determination of the calcium and magnesium content of corn was carried out using the Titrimetric method (AFNOR, 1986).

2.2.11 Determination of carbohydrates

Total Carbohydrates was expressed in percentage (%)

$\% \text{ carbohydrate} = 100\% - [\text{moisture content} + \text{ash content} + \text{total lipids} + \text{crude protein content}]$.

2.2.12 Preparation of Serial Dilution of Samples

Fifty grams (50g), of each weaning food was aseptically transferred to a Waring Blender and 450 ml of buffered dilution water and homogenized at approximately 8,000 rev/min as described by APHA. Dilutions of up to 10^{-37} were prepared in buffered dilution water as follows: 1ml of suspension of sample was transferred into a tube containing 9ml of sterile water and tube thoroughly mixed. This gave a 10^{-2} . From this tube, 1ml of sample was transferred into another tube containing 9ml and mixed to have a 10^{-3} dilution.

2.2.13 Determination of Total Coliform Load of Weaning Food Samples

Coliform counts were determined by plating 1ml of sample from the 10^{-3} dilution into a petri-dish. About 15ml of Violet Red Bile (VRB) agar at approximately 45°C was poured to the plate and swirled gently to ensure mixing of sample and agar. Plates were overlaid with 4 to 5 ml of the same agar, allowed to solidify and then incubated for 24 hours at 37°C . Samples were plated in duplicate. Red colonies with dark centres were counted and the average multiplied by the dilution factor. Counts were expressed as CFU/g.

2.2.14 Determination of the total viable bacterial load of Weaning Food sample

Total bacterial load of samples was determined using the pour plate method as described by ISO 8786.1. One millilitre of sample from 10^{-2} was transferred into a 9 cm Petri dish. Nutrient agar (Sigma-Aldrich) (about 45°C) was then poured into the plate and the plate swirled to mix the medium and sample. Plates were allowed to solidify and then incubated at 37°C for 48 hours. Samples were inoculated in triplicate. Total bacterial load was determined by multiplying the counts by the dilution factor. Counts were expressed as CFU/g.

2.2.15 Determination of the fungal load of Local Weaning Food sample

Total fungal load of weaning food samples was determined using the ISO horizontal methods for the enumeration of yeasts and moulds in foods as described by ISO 8786.1 One micro litre suspension of the weaning food containing small quantities of polysorbitan 80 (break up clumps

of mould spores and conidia), was spread over the surface of Sabouraud Dextrose agar (Sigma-Aldrich). Antibiotic was also added to inhibit bacteria growth. Plates were allowed to solidify and then incubated at room Temperature for 5 to 7 days and then examined daily for growth. Total fungal load was determined by multiplying the counts by the dilution factor. Counts were expressed as CFU/g.

2.2.16 Formulation of Maize Based Weaning Food

The weaning was formulated from the processed raw materials. Three samples were prepared based on the different concentrations of the carbohydrate based (maize), the protein base (snails and crayfish). The samples were prepared from flour of soya bean, snails, maize and crayfish, in the following ratios (%w/w) 40:30:25:5, 43:33:20:4 and 20:55:20:5 of carbohydrate: protein soybeans: snails: and crayfish respectively. The respective inputs were thoroughly mixed to produce a homogenous blend of the meal. The different end products were then subjected to sensory evaluation.

Table 1: Product Formulations Based on Concentration (%)

	Yellow Maize	Soy Beans	Snails	Crayfish
Sample 1	40	30	25	5
Sample 2	43	33	20	4
Sample 3	20	55	20	5

Source: Field work, 2023

2.2.17 Sensory evaluation

The test was conducted by using 15 trained panellists (nursing mothers) with children with age six months to 12 months. Consumers were asked to fill questionnaires prepared for the evaluated sensory attributes of the samples. That is colour, taste, smell, mouth feel and overall acceptability using a 4-point dislike scale (1=strongly dislike 4= strongly like) as described by Lawless and Heyman (2010).

Proximal Determination of Weaning Food

Water and Dry Matter Content

The determination of the dry matter was carried out according to the AFNOR method of 1982. The water and volatile matter content noted H is deduced from the dry matter content by the formula:

$$\% H = 100 - DM$$

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Results of Sensory Evaluation of the Weaning Food

Figure 5 below displays the responses that the respondents gave concerning their sensory evaluation of sample 1 (Which came out to be the best sample after sensory evaluation).

Table 2: Sensory Evaluation of Sample One

	Strongly Dislike	Dislike	Like	Strongly Like
Color	02	01	08	04
Smell	02	02	08	03
Texture	01	02	08	04
Taste	03	01	07	05
Sweetness	02	02	08	03
Overall acceptability	01	02	08	04

Source: Field work, 2023

Figure 1: Sensory Evaluation of Sample One

3.2 Results for Proximate Analysis

The carbohydrate content (Table 3, Figure 14) in the prepared weaning diets were all significantly different from each other at $p > 0.05$. Sample one had the highest carbohydrate concentration of 48.26mg/100MS. This high carbohydrate concentration results from the maize being the main source of carbohydrate in the weaning food. The carbohydrate levels of the prepared weaning food were higher than the lower limit for carbohydrates (41.13 to 73.79g/100 g) of the Codex Alimentarius Standards. These results are in line with reports of other researches on local weaning food (Tiencheu *et al.*, 2016; Asoba *et al.*, 2018).

The protein contents of the weaning diets are as shown on Table 5. Protein is one of the most important nutrients required in weaning foods. Samples one, two and three had values of protein content which were above minimum amount (14.52%) specified in Codex Alimentarius standards (2015). The high protein contents of the formulations were contributed by the snails, soy bean and cray fish.. According to FAO/WHO Codex Alimentarius Standards for weaning foods, the

protein content should range from 14.52 to 37.70 g/100 g for maximum complementation of amino acids in foods and growth (2018). Thus, the formulations satisfy the protein demands of weaning foods for infants (Asoba *et al.*, 2018).

The fat contents of the weaning diets are as shown on Table 3. The fat contents of sample one was slightly higher than that of samples two and three. The fat contents of the formulated diets are higher than the recommended fat level for weaning foods which should be less than 10% (Tiencheu *et al.*, 2016). The fat content of a food sample can affect its shelf stability. This is because fat can undergo oxidative deterioration, which leads to food spoilage. Hence a food sample with high fat content is more liable to spoilage than one with a lower fat content. Furthermore, high intake of fat especially saturated fatty acids has been shown to increase the level of cholesterol in the blood; however, this is not the case with unsaturated fats such as fat found in soybean and cereals (Pandey and Singh, 2018). Hence the formulated diets are suitable for weaning foods.

The energy contents are as shown on Table 3. The high energy content of sample one could be attributed to its high carbohydrate content as well as its high fat content relative to samples two and three. For all the weaning foods the energy density per 100 g of the dry food was lower than the minimum energy (483.9kcal/100g) recommended in the Codex Alimentarius Standards for weaning foods (2018). Dewey stated that energy needs from complementary foods for infants and toddlers who are still breastfed vary (2015).

The results for ash contents are as shown on Table 3. The ash content of the products, which gives an idea of the mineral content, was highest in sample one. All samples had ash contents acceptable by the Protein Advisory Group standard which recommended that the ash content should not exceed 5% (Tiencheu *et al.*, 2016). No standard for ash content has been specified for weaning foods in the Codex Alimentarius Standards (2018) (Tiencheu *et al.*, 2016). The high amounts of mineral were contributed by the snails which are very rich in minerals. Minerals are essential in infants and young children for building bones and teeth, functioning of muscles and nerves, blood clotting, synthesis of haemoglobin (an oxygen carrier in the red blood cells), myoglobin (used for muscle contraction) and enzymes/coenzymes (used in various metabolic path-ways) enhancement of the body's immune system thus, reducing infections and fostering proper functioning of other organs of the body and for immune defence (Asoba *et al.*, 2018).

Table 3: Results for Proximate Analysis

Weaning Food Sample	Carbohydrate (mg/100MS)	Protein (mg/100MS)	Fat (mg/100MS)	Ash content (mg/100MS)	Energy content (mg/100MS)	Dry matter (mg/100MS)
Sample 1	48.26	21.97	10.93	2.97	15.40	86.60

Source: Field work, 2023

From the above table and the results obtained, the carbohydrate content of the best sample following sensory analysis (Sample 1) was 48.26g/100g Pdt. The protein content was 21.97g/100g Pdt, fat content was 10.93g/100g Pdt, Ash (mineral) content was 2.97mg/100g Pdt, Energy content was 15.4Kcal, Dry matter was 86.60mg/100g Pdt. The most abundant mineral was

calcium 87.03mg/100g Pdt, Magnesium was 16.00mg/100g Pdt, Iron content was 3.20mg/100gPdt.

Source: Field work, 2023

Figure 2: Proximate Analysis of Sample One

3.3 Results for Mineral Analysis

The formulated weaning foods have been shown to contain high amounts of calcium, magnesium and iron (Table 4). Calcium is a macromineral important in bone and teeth formation. Magnesium another macromineral is an important co-factor in many enzymes. Iron is an important trace mineral that functions in carrying oxygen-rich haemoglobin to the rest of the body. In all, sample one had the highest Calcium, magnesium and iron content (Tiencheu *et al.*, 2016). Snails are known to be very rich sources of iron and are highly consumed for their enriching nutrient and health benefits. In essence, the main source of iron in this weaning food can be said to come from the snail (Asoba *et al.*, 2018).

To achieve protein and micronutrient density, complementary feeding guidelines recommend the addition of animal-source foods (ASFs) to plant-based foods (Agbemaflé *et al.*, 2020). Animal-source foods do not only increase nutrient density of complementary foods, but also improve bioavailability of micronutrients (Gibson *et al.*, 2012; Hurrell *et al.*, 2003). For example, ASFs not only provide bioavailable iron but also enhance the bioavailability of non-heme iron from other foods in the diet (Hurrell *et al.*, 2003).

Table 4: Results for Mineral Analysis

Sample	Calcium (Ca)(mg/100MS)	Magnesium (Mg) (mg/100MS)	Iron (Fe) (mg/100MS)
Sample 1	87.03	16.00	3.20

Source: Field work, 2023

Source: Field work, 2023

Figure 3: Mineral Content of Sample One

3.4 Results of Microbial Analysis and Shelf-life Studies

According to the report of WHO (2000) microbial contamination of weaning foods can be prevented by using safe water for preparation, frequent washing of hands and proper storage. However, in low income settings this can be constrained by lack of economic resources and absence of facilities for storage of food (Obi and Nwozor, 2012). Table 5 is an assessment of the microbial content of the formulated food. Going by the International Commission for Microbiological Specification for Foods (ICMSF) guidelines, between week 0 and week 12 the Bacterial, Coliform and Fungal Loads in the formulated food were within satisfactory levels ($<10^5$ CfU/g) and the formulated food is safe to consume within this period. These results are in line with reports of other researchers (Omemu and Omeke, 2010; Degaga *et al.*, 2015).

Beyond week 12, the Bacterial load slipped into the borderline region (10^5 to $<10^6$ CfU/g) even when Coliform and Fungal loads are still within the satisfactory range so that the food may still be consumed without adverse effect. However because most infants have an immune system that is not fully developed, it will be unwise to put them at risk and it is best to peg the shelf life to a duration within which the formulated food is without a doubt, safe to consume and this is 12 weeks immediately after production.

Table 5: Results for Microbial and shelf-life studies

Duration of Storage	Total Bacterial Count (Cfu/g)	Total Fungal Count (Cfu/g)	Total Coliform Count (Cfu/g)
Week 1	7.1×10^{-5}	1×10^{-6}	2.2×10^{-5}
Week 2	14.2×10^{-5}	2×10^{-6}	4.4×10^{-5}
Week 3	28.4×10^{-5}	4×10^{-6}	8.8×10^{-5}
Week 4	56.8×10^{-5}	6×10^{-6}	17.6×10^{-5}
Week 5	113.6×10^{-5}	8×10^{-6}	35.2×10^{-5}

Week 6	227.2×10^{-5}	10×10^{-6}	70.4×10^{-5}
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Source: Field work, 2023

Source: Field work, 2023

Figure 4: Microbial Content of Weaning Food after Six Weeks of Storage

Source: Field work, 2023

Figure 5: Line Graph of Microbial Content of Weaning Food after Six Weeks of Storage

Source: Field work, 2023

Figure 6: Fungal, Bacteria and Coliform Loads of Weaning Food

3.5 Packaging of Weaning Food

The food package is designed in line with Codex Standards for food packaging material thus in containers which will safeguard the hygienic and other qualities of the food.

The package is also properly labelled following the Codex standards clearly stating the name of the food, ingredients found in the food, the declaration of nutritive value of the food, utilization information, storage information, place of origin of food, date of manufacture, business name and address, including all basic information necessary for helping the consumer make informed decision.

Source: Field work, 2023

Figure 6: Designed Package for the Weaning Food

4 Conclusion

This project realized a weaning food from maize, soybean, snails and crayfish flour. It has shown that the complementary food with seed legumes and animal-food sources such as snails could boost the protein level in weaning foods. It also played a role in providing micronutrients like minerals and vitamins, especially calcium, magnesium and iron. The roasting process employed in the study (roasting of soybean) played a role in reducing the relatively high level of anti-nutrients associated with leguminous food sources. The process also influenced low moisture content of the products during the drying process which is important for transportation and extension of the shelf life of properly packaged products.

The weaning food is packaged in line with Codex Standards as the package will safeguard the hygienic and other qualities of the food. It is also properly labelled following the Codex standards with declaration of the nutritive value of the food and all basic information necessary for helping the consumer make informed decision. Thus could serve as a potential product to add variety to those in the market.

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